

A Holistic Evaluation of Femicide

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1

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Abstract

The death of women and girls as a direct consequence of gender-based violence is referred to as femicide. It is a widespread issue that affects women of various ages, colors, and socioeconomic situations all over the world. As a multifaceted issue, femicide calls for an all-encompassing analysis so that its underlying factors may be comprehended and workable remedies can be devised. Examining the social, cultural, economic, and political elements that contribute to the issue of femicide is an essential component of a comprehensive analysis of the problem. Women are often seen to be less capable than males, and as a direct consequence, they are more likely to be victims of prejudice and abuse. This has the potential to rise to a culture of violence towards women in which femicide is accepted and may even be justified. This study is particularly significant since it contributes a holistic viewpoint to the existing body of femicide research, which is a crucial aspect of the topic.

Keywords: Health, Disability Legal Regulations, Psychological, Social, Ministry Ugh Health, Women, Femicides, Violence, Discrimination, Justice

INTRODUCTION

Femicide, which refers to the intentional killing of women and girls because of their gender, is a widespread issue that affects women all over the globe. According to Campbell (2003), femicide is the most severe type of gender-based violence, which may also entail torturing, mutilating, persecuting, and sexually assaulting a victim. This piece will investigate the topic of femicide, focusing on its origins as well as the effects it has on society. Femicide is a complicated problem that calls for a strategy that takes into account a variety of factors if one wants to get to the bottom of what drives it and stop it from happening.

AIM

The purpose of this study is to conduct an analysis of femicide from the viewpoint of a holistic approach. Femicide has a detrimental impact on societies all over the globe in terms of social aspects, cultural aspects, political aspects, and even economic aspects.

METHOD

In this particular study, one of the qualitative research methodologies known as literature research was used. The qualitative research method of doing a literature review comes with a number of benefits and drawbacks. The use of qualitative data enables researchers to investigate their topics of interest in more depth, giving particular attention to the reasons behind, the progression of, and the goals served by actions and occurrences. In the field of psychiatry, difficult research problems are able to benefit from qualitative research. The usage of focus groups is advocated as an efficient approach and technique for gaining a more in-depth understanding of human phenomena, in particular those that are associated with the learning process and the primary players involved in it. On the other hand, the response that is provided by this method is somewhat general and does not include any specific quantitative values. Nevertheless, in terms of femicides, this research approach is the one that is going to yield the most information within the confines of the scope of this study.

RESULTS

The murdering of women and girls because of their gender is referred to as femicide, and it is a phrase that has been around for quite some time. It is a kind of gender-based violence that is often carried out by intimate

CURRENT SCIENCE

partners or members of the same family. Femicide is a widespread issue that impacts women and girls of different ages, colors, and socioeconomic origins all across the world. In spite of the ubiquity of the act, there is no one term that can be applied to all cases of femicide; instead, several nations and organizations have developed their own definitions (Campbell, 2003). One definition of femicide is offered by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), which describes it as "the deliberate killing of women because they are women." Another definition of femicide is offered by the American Psychological Association. According to Guedes et al. (2016), this definition includes homicides that are motivated by gender-based discrimination, such as honor killings, dowry-related murders, and murders committed in the name of tradition or culture. The United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime makes a distinction between intimate partner femicide committed by a current or former partner and intimate relationship femicide committed by a person who was not the victim's current or past partner. Femicide is defined as "the deliberate killing of women because they are women" by the World Health Organization (WHO), which is yet another meaning of the term. This definition encompasses homicides that are not based on gender but occur in the context of gender inequality, as well as killings that are based on gender but do not include discrimination against a particular gender.

In recent years, there has been a rising acknowledgment of the necessity to treat femicide as a distinct kind of violence against women. This is a development that has occurred as a result of the increased awareness of the issue. According to Garcia- Moreno et al. (2006), some nations have created particular laws to address femicide, while others have incorporated femicides in their more general laws on violence against women. Utilizing the Responsibility to Protect (R2P) ideology is one approach that may be used to combat the problem of femicide. The obligation to Protect (R2P) is a theory that was formed in 2005 by the United Nations to address the obligation of the international community to protect individuals from genocide, war crimes, crimes against humanity, and ethnic cleansing (Campbell, 2003). According to the National Institute of Justice (2017), there is a school of thought among academics that maintains victims of femicide and other forms of gender discrimination, such as transcode, should be afforded the same level of legal protection as victims of genocide. A significant issue that is plaguing the lives of women and young girls all over the globe is femicide. The intentional death of women because of their gender is usually acknowledged to constitute femicide, despite the fact that there is no one definition of femicide that is universally accepted. The problem of femicide calls for a multipronged strategy, which should include measures to prevent the crime, legislative changes, and increased responsibility for those who commit it.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The investigation of femicides is essential for a number of different reasons. To begin, it assists in the delivery of justice to victims and the relatives of those victims. Femicide is a crime that often does not result in any kind of punishment. It is possible for law enforcement to hold criminals responsible for their conduct and guarantee that justice is served by investigating these situations (Jewkes & Abrahams, 2002). Second, according to the World Health Organization (2014), doing research on femicides may assist in identifying patterns and trends in these types of murders. This knowledge may be put to use in the creation of preventative initiatives and policies that address the underlying factors that lead to femicide. agency of the European Union for basic Rights, 2018). For instance, research has shown that hearing about a femicide boosts people's expectations about the possibility of intimate partner violence in the future if any preventative measures are not done. Policymakers are able to devise targeted interventions that address the underlying causes of femicide if they first identify the patterns and trends that are associated with it.

Third, doing research on femicides is one way to assist in raising awareness about this problem. Femicide, in general, does not get an adequate amount of coverage in the media, which may contribute to a lack of public awareness about the severity of the issue (Stark, 2007). Journalism that focuses on investigation plays a significant part in both bringing these situations to light and increasing public awareness of the underlying problem. According to Campbell (2003), journalists have vital tasks to perform in the investigation of femicides. On the other hand, students need to be aware of the challenges that come with reporting on this matter. For instance, femicide cases are often difficult to solve and need for an in-depth knowledge of the many social and cultural aspects that play a role in the commission of these crimes.

Journalists have a responsibility to be considerate of the requirements that victims and their families have, while also ensuring that they report on these instances in an ethical and truthful manner. According to DeKeseredy and Schwartz (2016), conducting investigations into femicides is highly essential for a number of reasons, including but not limited to providing justice to victims and their families, determining patterns and trends in these crimes, devising preventative strategies and legislation, and increasing public awareness on this problem. According to the United Nations (2015), journalists have an essential part to play in the investigation of femicides; nevertheless, they must be aware of the challenges that come with reporting on this topic. It is possible for law enforcement, those who determine policy, and journalists to collaborate in order to aid in the prevention of femicide and guarantee that victims and their families get justice.

CURRENT SCIENCE

It has been going on for generations, but femicide, which refers to the act of killing women and girls because of their gender, is an issue that affects the whole world. Through the course of history, femicide has taken many different forms, ranging from the murder of young girls to the "honor killing" of women in many different countries. But the term "femicide" wasn't used to refer to it until Carol Orlock mentioned it. According to research published by the National Institute of Justice (2017), the investigation and prosecution of hate crimes in Latin America and the Caribbean do not adhere to any predefined norms. This includes hate crimes committed against women. The vast majority of information gathered on homicides does not include a gender breakdown of the cases. According to Rennison (2003), this leads to a significant number of cases of femicide being unsolved, particularly in regions experiencing armed conflict and places plagued by poverty. On the other hand, there have been some recent advancements in both the gathering of data on femicides and their accessibility. On a yearly basis, women make up around 17% of the total number of people who are killed intentionally all over the world, with an average of 66,000 being brutally murdered. Only in the year 2021, intimate partners or family members were responsible for the deaths of around 45,000 women and girls over the globe, according to research by UN Women. The perpetrators of femicides are by far the closest individuals and account for 65% of all intimate spouse and family-related killings. Femicides occur in the United States at an alarming rate. The number of deaths that are caused by intimate partner and family relationships has stayed pretty constant throughout the course of time. This demonstrates that the world is not succeeding in putting an end to fatalities that might have been avoided via early intervention, gender-sensitive police, access to justice, and victim-centered care and protection.

There has been a long and complicated history of women killing other women. In ancient Rome, if a father believed that his daughter was living an immoral lifestyle, he had the legal authority to have her executed. Women who were suspected of practicing witchcraft in medieval Europe were often put to death by being burnt at the stake. It is believed that between the 15th and 18th centuries, tens of thousands of women were put to death as a result of the witch hunts that occurred throughout Europe. In more modern times, femicides have been committed in a variety of ways. According to Campbell (2003) and other researchers, the desire for males has led to a long-standing culture of murdering female children in India. Even though it is against the law in several African nations, the practice of female genital mutilation is nonetheless common. Killings committed in the name of honor are still quite prevalent in Pakistan and other nations throughout South Asia and the Middle East. There are groups that provide help to victims of femicide in the countries of Italy, Switzerland, Spain, and the United Kingdom.

CURRENT SCIENCE

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the reporting and analysis of femicide rates in the United Kingdom. The United Kingdom in 2021 Observer and Femicide Under the direction of Census, a campaign has been launched to increase the detection of femicides, enhance the information available on this topic, and bring awareness to victims of violence. Since 2009, extensive and comparative statistics on femicide in the UK have been collected via the Femicide Census. This data includes information on demographics. Femicide is a crime that may take place in every civilization, but there are cultural and sociological variables that contribute to its frequency in certain societies more than others. The term "patriarchy" refers to a social structure in which males have main power and predominate in positions of political leadership, moral authority, social privilege, and property control. Patriarchy is also known as "the patriarchy." Because it encourages the concept that males are superior to women and that women should be subservient to men, patriarchy is a significant contributor to the phenomenon of femicide. When males believe that their authority or dominance is being challenged, this belief system may lead to acts of violence against women. Cultural norms might also lead to femicide. For instance, in many societies, it is customary for women to show males their submission by obeying their commands. When women fail to live up to these standards, they are punished with physical harm and sometimes even with their lives. According to the Institute of Justice (2017)). In addition, societal standards about masculinity may be a factor in femicide, particularly in situations in which males feel the need to demonstrate their manhood by acting violently against women. The economic climate is also one of the reasons that contributes to the problem of femicide. For instance, being poor and having a job might lead to feelings of stress and frustration, which can increase the risk of violent acts being committed against women. In addition, studies have shown that women who are economically reliant on their spouses are more likely to be victims of domestic violence since they have less choices for escaping abusive situations.

Inadequate education is another factor that may play a role in femicide. Women who have not completed their education may be at a greater risk of experiencing abuse either because they are less likely to be aware of their rights or because they lack the skills and resources necessary to escape violent situations. According to Jewkes and Abrahams (2002), a woman's immigration status may also be a factor in femicide. According to DeKeseredy and Schwartz (2016), immigrant women may be more susceptible to becoming victims of abuse because they may not be aware of their legal rights or may not have access to services that might assist them in leaving violent situations. Honor murders are a special kind of femicide in which a woman is murdered by a member of her own family because they believe she has brought disgrace or shame upon the family. Honor murders are a practice that are all too widespread in many areas of the globe, and they are often validated by cultural or religious beliefs. According to Guedes et al. (2016), intimate partner violence is an additional

CURRENT SCIENCE

element that contributes to femicide. When women are in relationships that are violent to them, they put themselves at danger of being murdered by their spouses. One of the factors that might lead to femicide is the absence of legal rights for women. When women are denied access to legal safeguards or when laws are not implemented, those who commit acts of violence against women may not be held accountable for their actions. One country that is dealing with the aftermath of femicide is Mexico, where the issue has grown in significance over the last several years. Only in the year 2020 were there a total of 3,752 femicides perpetrated in Mexico, as reported by the National Observatory on Citizen Femicides. When compared to the previous year, this is a 7.9% increase in growth. There has been a total of 452 documented occurrences of femicide in the state of Mexico. This makes Mexico the state with the highest rate.

The majority of femicides in Mexico are carried out by intimate partners or members of the same family. One such case of femicide may be found in South Africa, where the issue is quite prevalent. The South African Medical Research Council estimates that 2,695 women were taken from this world in South Africa between April 2019 and March 2020. When compared to the previous year, this is a 5% gain. The majority of these homicides were carried out by intimate partners or members of the same family. Another significant issue that has arisen in India is the rise of femicide. There were 4,05,861 instances of crimes against women in India in 2019, as reported by the National Criminal Record Office. There were 1,299 honor murders and 7,026 dowry-related fatalities in this total number of instances. Both of these methods are acts of femicide that are typical in India. In recent years, Turkey has seen an increase in the number of cases of femicide. Only in the year 2020 did Turkey see a staggering total of 300 femicides, as reported by the We Will Stop Femicide Platform. When compared to the prior year, this is a 32% increase. The majority of these homicides were carried out by intimate partners or members of the same family.

Femicide refers to the intentional death of a woman for reasons related to her gender. It is a global issue that plagues each and every nation and location on the face of the earth. There are a number of factors that might contribute to femicide, including detrimental societal norms, discrimination against women and girls, unbalanced power interactions between men and women, and traditional gender roles. There are two categories to consider while discussing femicide. These femicides take place in close quarters and are not kept confidential. The first category describes situations in which women are killed by their present or past husbands, whereas the second category describes situations in which women are killed by persons who are not intimately linked to them in any way. There is a good chance that the real number of femicides committed is far greater than the number that has been documented. However, femicide can be prevented via primary preventive activities that concentrate on changing harmful societal norms and including all groups and

CURRENT SCIENCE

cultures in the process of generating change. Discrimination, the presence of a culture of violence, impunity, and other elements are among the many factors that contribute to the widespread occurrence of femicides.

The prevalence of femicide is significantly influenced by gender inequality as well as patriarchal social structures. In patriarchal countries, violence against women is often normalized and regarded as an acceptable part of day-to-day life. According to Johnson et al. (2008), this might result in an increase in the number of women who are killed because males believe they have the right to use violence against women whom they believe do not comply to conventional gender norms. It is common for women in patriarchal settings to have restricted access to education, which may leave them more susceptible to femicide. Women may not be aware of their rights or know how to defend themselves against violence if they do not have access to education. It is possible that women in patriarchal society have restricted access to economic prospects, which leaves them economically reliant on males. Because of their addiction, women may find it difficult to escape violent relationships or to seek assistance when they are in danger. Patriarchal civilizations sometimes adhere to rigid gender norms, which prescribe how men and women should conduct themselves. These roles may contribute to femicide by promoting the concept that males have the right to control and dominate women. In turn, this can lead to women taking their own lives. Women who are victims of abuse may not get sufficient legal protection in patriarchal society due to the inadequacy of the legal system. Because of this, it may be difficult for abused women to seek safety or justice from their violent spouses. In addition, women who are victims of abuse may not have the support of their families or communities.

According to Johnson et al. (2008), in certain situations, members of the victim's family may blame the victim for the violence or put him under pressure to continue being in an abusive relationship. It is crucial to address the core causes of gender inequality and strive toward creating more equal societies (Coker et al., 2000). This is necessary in order to solve the problem of femicide in patriarchal civilizations. This can include educating both men and women on the importance of gender equality and respecting women's rights, providing women with access to education and economic opportunities so that they can become financially independent and less vulnerable to violence, and enforcing laws that protect women from being subjected to violence. We may work toward making this future a reality by providing victims of abuse with support services such as counseling, legal help, and secure housing; by questioning old gender norms; and by supporting and addressing more equitable interactions between men and women. Those are just some of the ways we can do this.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Both domestic femicide and spousal murder, two kinds of violence against women, have been the subject of a significant amount of research and critical examination in recent years. Domestic femicide refers to the killing of a woman by a member of the victim's immediate family, while partner femicide refers to the killing of a woman by her current or former romantic partner. Both types of violence are common in many nations across the globe and have major repercussions for the health and well-being of women who are victims of them. According to the findings of several studies, there are a variety of variables that have a role in domestic and spousal murders. The reaction of the criminal justice system to instances of violence against women is one of these (Coker et al., 2000). Other factors include gender stereotypes and conventional beliefs on domestic violence. In certain nations, for instance, the legal parameters of what constitutes "self-defense" are quite restricted, which might make it difficult for women to protect themselves against the violent acts of their partners. In addition, the connection between domestic violence and stalking is often misunderstood, which may result in harmful preconceptions about the manner in which occurrences of intimate partner femicide are reported.

In spite of these challenges, there have been some encouraging advances throughout the course of the last several years. For instance, in Brazil, the Maria da Penha Law reformed criminal proceedings and included integrated policies to cope with the complexities of gender-based violence (Campbell, 2003). As part of the changes, women-only police stations, specialist courts, intervention orders, multidisciplinary experts, and perpetrator programs were all introduced. In addition, a new legislation was created in 2015 with the intention of preventing 'honour killing' defenses in spousal murder cases, which constitute the crime of femicide, and to avoid impunity (DeKeseredy & Schwartz, 2016). However, further steps are need to be taken in order to address the issue of domestic and spousal femicide. This involves enhancing the reaction of the criminal justice system to incidents of violence against women, correctly naming situations that include femicide, and giving assistance to women who have been victims of abuse. In addition to this, it involves confronting preconceived notions about gender roles and conventional perspectives of family violence.

Femicides committed in the home or by intimate partners are among the most severe types of violence against women and deserve immediate attention from academics, policymakers, and practitioners. Both sexual femicide and sexual harassment are serious problems that impact women all over the globe. According to Johnson et al. (2008), the purpose of violence against women that is based on their gender is to maintain the social order that is a product of patriarchal society. It encompasses crimes like as discrimination, sexual harassment, rape, the use of women for prostitution, and any and all other forms of violence that cause women to suffer physically, sexually, and psychologically. The most severe form of gender-based violence is

CURRENT SCIENCE

femicide, which you can read more about here. This event marks the most lethal culmination in the long and gruesome history of men committing acts of violence and assault against women. Femicides have reached worrisome proportions all over the globe, despite the fact that successive governments have enacted laws with the goal of eradicating and preventing femicides (Krug et al., 2002). Despite this, the governments have not been able to accomplish their aims. Sexual harassment is a kind of gender-based violence that may occur in a range of contexts, including the workplace, educational institutions, and public areas. Women are disproportionately affected by this type of abuse. It includes making sexual approaches without permission, asking for sexual favors, and any other verbal or physical conduct of a sexual character, whether verbal or physical, that creates an atmosphere that is hostile or insulting.

Teaching models may be used by educators in the field of social work to educate social work students and professionals on the pervasive, violent, overt, and overt male controls and violence against women (Coker et al., 2000). This can help solve the problems that have been identified. Conversations on sexist language, gender-based research, discriminatory treatment, street talk, sexist media, pornography, sexual harassment, beatings, sexual assault, and femicide might be part of the instructional approach. It is imperative that measures be taken to raise awareness about these concerns and put into effect legislation that protect women from gender-based violence. It is imperative that governments take action to implement laws that make femicide and sexual harassment crimes. Policies that prevent sexual harassment in the workplace and at educational institutions and that give assistance to victims should be implemented in both settings. The culture of a society as a whole has a responsibility to make efforts to ensure that women's rights are respected and that gender equality is advanced.

Both the trade in women and the practice of forced prostitution are important issues that impact millions of women all over the globe. Women are often abducted for the purpose of sexual exploitation, and the prevalence of this issue has considerably expanded as a result of globalization. During the 2006 World Cup, the problem of forced prostitution and human trafficking was brought up in public discourse and anti-trafficking initiatives in various nations, such as Germany. The method used in Scandinavia to prevent human trafficking for sexual reasons has been presented as a potential solution to this problem. On the other hand, the legal treatment of prostitution and the degree to which it is connected to the struggle against the sex trade might vary from one jurisdiction to another. The present conversation on human trafficking has mostly centered on the exploitation of women and children for sexual purposes, but it is critical to highlight the existence of people who are coerced into working in other industries. Women who are trafficked for the purpose of sexual exploitation often come from impoverished backgrounds and are more susceptible to being

CURRENT SCIENCE

exploited. Women who have been trafficked for the purpose of sexual exploitation need to develop a strong sense of resilience in order to heal and advance in their lives.

It is counterproductive to the development of methods to combat human trafficking to focus on trafficking for the purpose of prostitution since this hides some of the underlying reasons of trafficking and ignores the enormous number of women who are transported into other industries. The complex problems of forced prostitution and the trafficking of women necessitate a response that incorporates a variety of perspectives. It is essential to recognize the precarious position of women who have been subjected to human trafficking, investigate the fundamental issues that contribute to this issue, and devise solutions that go beyond a singular concentration on human trafficking for the sake of prostitution. Resilience is another crucial component in assisting trafficked women on their road to recovery and growth.

Femicide, which refers to the act of murdering a woman because of her gender, has grave repercussions that not only impact the victims but also their family and the communities in which they lived. The mental health of women who have been victims of intimate partner violence, a kind of femicide, is much poorer, and they are significantly more likely to entertain suicide ideas. According to Campbell (2003), persistent mental problems were also shown to have a substantial association with any experience of violence. Regrettably, a significant number of incidents of partner violence against women do not get reported, and legal complaints concerning physical abuse are not always filed in every instance. According to the National Institute of Justice (2017), only approximately one-third of victims of intimate partner abuse in Europe have previously reported the incident to the police or another agency. Those who break from the usual gender norms are penalized with violence that may amount to femicide, and this reinforces the patriarchal system that places women in subservient positions to males.

The majority of homicides committed against women are never brought to justice, which contributes to a culture of impunity and reinforces the concept that violence against women is acceptable. Fear and trauma are created in communities as a result of femicide, particularly among women who are frightened for their own safety as well as the safety of others they care about. Loss of life is the most evident and tragic consequence of femicide. According to Campbell (2003), women who are slain because of their gender are cheated out of their future and their opportunity to make a positive contribution to society. Additionally, there may be financial repercussions for families and communities as a result of femicide. Women who are murdered may be contributing to the family financially or may have ambitions for their educational or

CURRENT SCIENCE

professional futures. It sheds light on important social justice concerns such as femicide, gender inequality, violence against women, and the need for legal and political changes to preserve women's rights. The effects of femicide are far-reaching and extend beyond the individual victims to include the victims' relatives and the communities in which they live. In addition to tackling the underlying causes of femicide, such as gender inequality and patriarchal institutions, it is necessary to give assistance to victims and hold offenders responsible for their acts. Providing support to victims and holding perpetrators accountable for their actions is a crucial step toward ending femicide. The psychological repercussions of violence against women extend well beyond the women who are directly targeted. Members of the family, particularly children, who see or are subjected to violence may also suffer from mental health issues such as anxiety, sadness, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Children who are raised in households where there is physical or emotional abuse are at a much-increased risk of becoming victims or aggressors of violence later in life.

It is necessary to identify the variables and causes responsible for domestic violence and its psychological impacts on women from a variety of angles. This will allow for a more comprehensive understanding of the problem. There is a need for improved processes, including the establishment of a culture in which victims of sexual and gender-based violence may confidently disclose their experiences without fear of retaliation and know that their stories will be treated seriously and kept private. According to the Institute of Justice (2017)). It is very necessary for victims of violence against women to have access to support services and other resources, as this will assist them in coping with the psychological impacts of the abuse. The victims of violence against women and their family often suffer from severe psychological repercussions as a result. This is a public health concern that has to be addressed by enhancing existing systems, increasing access to support services and resources, and conducting awareness campaigns in order to cultivate a culture in which SGBV is no longer tolerated.

Both violence against women and femicide have a destructive impact on the economies of the countries in which they occur. Damage done to innocent people as a result of this kind of violence has far-reaching and long-lasting effects. An examination of the relevant literature reveals that there was a surge in violent acts committed against children and women during the COVID-19 epidemic. This violence is frequently unintentionally replicated within families, and it serves as a symptom of a conscious lack of difference between families and the cultural, socio-economic norms of the settings in which they are immersed. In other

CURRENT SCIENCE

words, there is a conscious lack of differentiation between families and the violence that is prevalent in the situations in which they are immersed. According to Campbell (2003), violence against women is a reflection of unequal development as well as structural changes that produce insecurity based on gender. In the majority of nations, more people are killed or maimed as a result of violence against women during times of peace than during times of conflict. It is baffling that gender-based violence still exists in many parts of the globe, particularly in nations where middle-income modernization is taking place. The patterns of various types of social conflict that are connected to inequality, urban overpopulation, and bad governance are mirrored in the patterns of gender-based violence.

found that the ethnicity of a province, the prevalence of divorce, the amount of gender equality in schooling, and the level of economic growth are all important predictors of femicide. The growth of the economy may not be enough to stop women from killing one other, but it can minimize the impact of men's retaliation to women who question the status quo. In many nations in Latin America and the Caribbean, violence against women is a significant threat to national security. According to Guedes et al. (2016), the rates of homicide and femicide in these nations are among the highest seen elsewhere in the world. It is uncommon for there to be just one instance of violence against a woman. It is often the end consequence of intricate cycles of being victimized and put through agony. There is an infinite number of ways in which violence against women and femicide may affect a country's economy. It consists of a decline in economic growth, a loss of productivity as a result of injury or death, a rise in the cost of medical treatment, a fall in the educational levels of girls and women, a reduction in the number of women who participate in the labor force, an increase in the rate of poverty experienced by families headed by women, and so on. In addition to having a severe impact on physical health, violence against women may also have a detrimental effect on mental health. This can result in conditions such as depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and other mental health issues, all of which can have an adverse effect on job performance and productivity.

It is necessary to consider the political and social repercussions of femicide, which is defined as the murdering of women due to their gender. In today's Turkey, gender-based violence and sexist political discourse are ingrained and pervasive characteristics of society. According to Guedes et al. (2016), the normative remarks made by politicians regarding gender have the potential to rebuild the category of "real women" as a category with institutional and social ramifications that put the safety of women in jeopardy. It is possible to attribute the absence of justice in femicide cases in Juarez and Tijuana to the establishment of a patriarchal society as well as institutionalized forms of corruption. According to Campbell (2003), violence against women is a violation of human rights that also has specific justifications and is a developing paradox of progress and

CURRENT SCIENCE

globalization. Contradictory development, flaws in democracy, social inequality, uneven urbanization, and gender role inequity are all international risk factors that contribute to the insecurity of women throughout the globe in terms of their physical safety.

Violence against women also results as a societal emotion that fades from the public imagination as a true reality of this terrible and unconditional violence against women. Femicide is a socio-political construction by the principles of capitalism, and violence against women is also a byproduct of this creation. According to the Institute of Justice (2017)). Throughout their whole lives, women confront unique dangers in every region of the world. From child abuse to customary violence and forced marriage in adolescence, from sexual assault to femicide in adolescence and youth, it covers forced labor and beating in adulthood and the targeted killing of witches and widows in old age. It also covers female fetishism, female genital mutilation/circumcision in infancy. According to Guedes et al. (2016), women's resistance to femicide is often underreported and under classified. Critical thinkers have a responsibility to give serious attention to the personal narratives of women and girls. Because of the significant political and societal repercussions of femicide, measures including educational and awareness campaigns, as well as changes to existing institutions, need to be taken.

Femicide, which is the act of murdering a woman just because she is a woman, is a worldwide issue that needs measures for both prevention and response. It is possible to lower the risk of femicide through raising awareness among people, families, and communities about gender-based violence and the ways in which it affects women. Femicide may be prevented in part by women speaking out against violence and reaching out for assistance when they feel they need it. It may be possible to reduce the incidence of femicide through strengthening laws and policies that protect women from violence. According to Campbell (2003), one way to assist in the prevention of femicides is by holding both people and institutions responsible for their acts. It is vital to collect trustworthy statistics on the occurrence of femicide as well as information on the context in which it occurs in order to identify effective preventative methods. It is possible to reduce the incidence of femicide by providing victims of gender-based violence with support services including counseling, shelters, and legal assistance. It is possible to reduce the risk of femicide by ensuring that law enforcement agents have enough training to appropriately react to incidents of gender-based violence. The prevention of femicides may be aided by the fortification of various institutions, such as the judicial system and service providers.

Developing new methods of prevention and putting them to the test are two ways to assist avoid femicide. It is essential to keep in mind that the methods used to prevent femicides vary depending on the meaning of the

CURRENT SCIENCE

term "femicides" and the specific instances that are being discussed. For instance, avoiding femicide in relationships between intimate partners is not the same as preventing the slavery and death of trafficked women or girls. Consequently, it is essential to devise preventative techniques that are particular to the setting. According to the National Institute of Justice (2017), femicide is a complicated problem that calls for a strategy with several facets. Education, empowerment, legal action, leadership and accountability, and the accumulation of data need to be the primary focuses of prevention efforts, while the primary focuses of reaction tactics ought to be support services, law enforcement, institutional strengthening, and preventative innovation. By putting these tactics into practice, we may contribute to the global effort to decrease the number of occurrences of femicide.

Femicide, which refers to the killing of women and girls because of their gender, is a worldwide issue that impacts the lives of millions of people. It has been suggested that combating this issue might be accomplished by educational and awareness efforts. There is no particular research on the efficacy of education and awareness programs aimed at preventing femicide; however, there are studies on efforts very similar to those aimed at preventing other types of violence. For instance, Guedes et al. (2016) discovered that diabetes awareness and understanding may be increased by the use of quality education programs. This was observed in research that looked at diabetes education campaigns in the United Kingdom. In a similar vein, research conducted in Poland to investigate public knowledge and attitudes towards antibiotics indicated that repeated awareness efforts had the potential to alter both knowledge and attitudes.

Education and awareness initiatives, taken as a whole, have the potential to be beneficial in improving understanding and altering attitudes towards certain topics. However, in order to develop campaigns that are successful, it is essential to take into consideration the socioeconomic and cultural context of the problem that is being tackled. Education and awareness efforts about femicide should be adapted to the particular communities and cultures involved in order to have the greatest possible effect. According to the Institute of Justice (2017)). In order for these initiatives to be properly implemented, it is essential to include a wide variety of stakeholders, including the government, educational centers, researchers, and advocacy campaigns. By raising people's awareness and education levels on femicides, we may work toward avoiding the sad loss of life that would result from them. The primary social and cultural elements that lead to femicides may be addressed via the use of community-based interventions, which have been suggested as a method for preventing femicides. Even though there hasn't been a lot of research done on community-based treatments that are expressly aimed at preventing femicide, there is evidence that suggests these kinds of interventions may be successful in addressing factors that are associated to femicide, such as mental health, loneliness, and

CURRENT SCIENCE

alcohol use. Community-based methods may lessen the effect of risk factors such as social isolation and loneliness, according to the findings of a thorough evaluation of community-based treatments for the prevention and promotion of mental health in older individuals in the United Kingdom (Campbell, 2003).

In a similar vein, qualitative research conducted in England indicated that older persons with loneliness symptoms typically had awareness of local social and community resources, but they did not believe community- and primary care-based services to be effective for combating their feelings of isolation at this stage in their life. On the other hand, it was believed that participation in activities involving groups of people with shared interests was preferable than individual assistance. Another research assessed the effect of two community-based education interventions on Nigerian adults' awareness about the human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination and cervical screenings, as well as their intentions to obtain or support the vaccine and screenings. According to the findings of the research, gender-specific and context-specific low-cost community-based education interventions were successful in raising HPV vaccination rates and cervical cancer screening rates in sub-Saharan Africa. According to the Institute of Justice (2017)). According to the findings of a scoping assessment of community-based oral health treatments for persons who are experiencing homelessness, interventions have to incorporate co-design with homeless service users. The study brought to light a number of suggestions and identified a number of holes in the existing literature. Because of these limitations, it is necessary to take a deeper look at the role of non-clinical oral health treatments and increase the number of programs that target the homeless population.

One last piece of research examined the evidence for community-based treatments that are helpful in lowering alcohol intake and related negative effects among adults. According to the findings of the research, community mobilization, law enforcement, and media campaigns are all useful components of community-based interventions that target structural determinants of health. Even though there hasn't been a lot of study done on community-based treatments that particularly target femicide, there is evidence to suggest that these kinds of interventions may be beneficial when addressing the problems that are associated to it. Approaches based on the community have the potential to mitigate the negative effects of risk factors such as social isolation and loneliness. According to Garcia-Moreno et al. (2006), low-cost population-based educational initiatives that concentrate on gender and context are helpful in raising HPV vaccination and cervical screening rates. Co-designing interventions with service recipients is something that should always happen. In order to address the structural factors that determine health, community-based interventions that included law enforcement, media campaigns, and community mobilization proved to be successful components.

CONCLUSION

Femicide, which refers to the act of murdering women just for the fact that they are female, is a worldwide phenomenon that has been prominent for decades. Femicide rates continue to climb in many countries despite attempts to enhance data collecting and raise awareness of the issue. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) are spearheading efforts to enhance the data collection and assessment of gender-based killings against women and girls. On the other hand, there is a dearth of precise data on femicides, which makes it impossible to properly appreciate the scope of the issue and devise remedies that are successful. Abuse against women may come in a variety of ways, including verbal abuse, emotional abuse, physical abuse, and sexual assault, amongst others.

According to Garcia- Moreno et al. (2006), femicide is the most severe type of violence against women and is often carried out by husbands or other members of the victim's family. The connection between intimate relationship violence and femicide has been the topic of a significant amount of study, and the findings of this research indicate that women who have been a victim of intimate partner violence have a significantly increased chance of being murdered by their spouses. The rates of femicide are quite variable from country to country, with some nations having far higher rates than others. The Gender Equality Observatory found that Honduras, the Dominican Republic, and El Salvador had the highest rates of femicide in their countries. Mexico, particularly Ciudad Additionally, it is one of the top nations in terms of the number of femicides that take place each year, particularly in the city of Juárez. Beginning in the early 1990s, Mexico had a rise in the rate of violence against women, which was then followed by a spate of sexual assaults and acts of torture. Femicide rates have continued to climb in recent years (Campbell, 2003), despite the fact that the problem has received attention on a global scale and that attempts have been made to combat it. The public's understanding of femicide is significantly influenced by the media's portrayal of the topic. An analysis of newspaper stories revealed that coverage in the media often contributes to the perpetuation of damaging preconceptions about women and fails to depict the subject of femicide in an appropriate manner. The research also found that the media has a propensity to concentrate on individual incidents rather than systemic concerns, which may lead to a lack of awareness of the fundamental factors that contribute to femicide.

In order to combat femicide, it is necessary to have an understanding of the factors that contribute to the problem and to devise measures that are efficient in preventing it. This involves taking action to address gender inequalities, supporting education that is gender-sensitive, working to improve access to justice for

CURRENT SCIENCE

victims, and offering support services for survivors. Improving the gathering of data on femicide is also necessary in order to better understand the scale of the problem and design more focused responses. As a consequence, femicide is a complicated problem that calls for a strategy that considers a variety of angles. While there has been some improvement in terms of the gathering of data and the raising of awareness around femicide, there is still more work that needs to be done in order to stop these senseless crimes from occurring. We can make the world a place where no woman has to worry about being subjected to violence or prejudice if we all pull together to find solutions to the underlying problems that lead to femicide and come up with effective preventative methods.

LIMITATION

In light of the fact that the qualitative research technique was used in the course of this investigation, there are certain constraints that will result from this. It's possible that the conclusions of qualitative research can't be generalized because of the tiny sample sizes used in the study. Research that is qualitative may also be susceptible to possible bias in the replies as well as bias due to self-selection. The methods that the data collector uses, in addition to their own distinctive observations, have the potential to subtly modify the data, which would therefore reduce the reliability of the conclusions. The method of doing qualitative research takes a lot of time, which may limit its applicability to certain kinds of projects. It is possible for the efficacy of qualitative research to be hindered by factors such as inconsistency between the research topic and the technique, poor understanding of the methodology, and a lack of attention to the philosophical roots of the field.

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